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AN ANALYSIS OF INDIAN PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS USING CAMEL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Financial institutions are paramount tools in economy to boost the economic growth, especially banks are one of them. After the economic reforms 1991, Liberalization, privatization, globalization (LPG) growth of private sector banks increase tremendously. Private Banks contributes significantly in growth of economy. Initially banks are only limited to deposits and credits but today banks are perform various functions. Before to privatization of banks all financial needs of corporate and individual are meet by public sector banks but after privatization private sector banks also not behind the public sector banks to provide the credit facilities and other non banking services to individual and corporate. Many studies revels that private sector banks are better perform to public sector bank in terms of NPA management, profit making and other so more. To know the financial performance of private sector banks present study is conducted. In present study, researcher takes a sample of 5 private sector banks namely ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, HDFC Bank, Yes Bank, Indusland Bank and try to understand and analysis the financial performance and soundness of selected private sector banks during 2011-2016 through CAMEL methodology. CAMEL is an acronym where C- Capital Adequacy, A- Assets Quality, M- Management Efficiency, E- Earning Efficiency, L- Liquidity. Data used in study purely in secondary nature and collected from annual reports of respective banks, journal articles and other published documents.

Keywords: Indian private sector banks, financial performance, CAMEL

INTRODUCTION

Financial institutions are paramount tools in economy to boost the economic growth, especially banks are one of them financial institution. After the economic reforms 1991, Liberalization, privatization, globalization (LPG) growth of private sector banks increase tremendously. Private Banks contributes significantly in growth of economy. Initially banks are only limited to deposits and credits but today banks are perform various functions. Before to privatization of banks all financial needs of corporate and individual are meet by public sector banks but after privatization private sector banks also not behind the public sector banks to provide the credit facilities and other non banking services to individual and corporate. Many studies revels that private sector banks are better perform to public sector bank in terms of NPA management, profit making and other so more.

The banking sector's performance is perceived as the replica of economic activities of the economy. The stage of development of the banking industry is a good reflection of the development of the economy. There is a substantial improvement over the earlier supervisory system of banking sector in terms of recovery, management efficiency, assets quality, earning quality and internal control system to regulate the level of risk and financial viability of commercial banks. The regulators have augmented bank supervision by using CAMEL (capital adequacy, asset quality, management quality, earnings and liquidity) rating criterion to assess and evaluate the performance and financial soundness of the activities of the bank. The CAMEL supervisory criterion in banking sector is a significant and considerable improvement over the earlier criteria in terms of frequency, check, spread over and concentration. During this period, the banking sector has experienced a paradigm change and it was the time to make performance appraisal of operations. Reserve Bank of India recommended two supervisory rating models named as CAMELS (Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management, Earning, Liquidity, Systems and Controls) and CACS (Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Compliance, Systems and Controls) for rating of Indian commercial Banks and Foreign Banks operating in India (Misra & Aspal, 2013).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature provides the roadmap to researcher who wants to study the problem and reveals the undisclosed facts and results. There have vast literature on financial performance analysis of banks through ratio analysis only but limited by CAMEL methodology. Researcher reviews the published literature on financial performance analysis through CAMEL methodology prior to conduct of research article.

Svetlana Tatuskar (2010) analyzed the financial performance of selected Indian scheduled bank through CAMEL model. They had taken a sample of five banks namely ICICI bank, SBI, Axis bank, HDFC bank and BOI for study purpose. This study found that public sector banks like BOI had done remarkable well on every CAMEL parameter. In the case of private sector banks ICICI bank was outperformed the other private sector banks. Study show that public sector bank should formulate strong structure to recover of bad-assets.

Sushendra Kumar Misra and Parvesh Kumar Aspal (2013) conducted a study to evaluate the performance & financial soundness of State Bank Group using CAMEL approach. In this study, researchers evaluate and financial performance of through twenty ratio from the year 2009-2011. They found It is found that in terms of Capital Adequacy parameter SBBJ and SBP were at the top position, while SBI got lowest rank. In terms of Asset Quality parameter, SBBJ held the top rank while SBI held the lowest rank. Under Management efficiency parameter it was observed that top rank taken by SBT and lowest rank taken by SBBJ. In terms of Earning Quality parameter the capability of SBM got the top rank while SBP was at the lowest position. Under the Liquidity parameter SBI stood on the top position and SBM was on the lowest position. SBI needs to improve its position with regard to asset quality and capital adequacy, SBBJ should improve its management efficiency and SBP should improve

its earning quality. They also employed ANOVA statistic to test hypothesis. By ANOVA result they found there have no significant difference in performance of SBI and its associate banks.

An another study conducted by Santosh Kumar and Roopali Sharma (2014) to evaluate performance of top Indian bank through CAMEL methodology. In research study, they decided to evaluate the top 8 market capitalized banks. Kotak Mahindra Bank is on top position in term of capital adequacy. They also found that SBI had highest NPA among their peer banks. They opinion that earning quality of SBI and PNB was on top. They concluded from the study that Kotal Mahindra and ICICI bank was most efficient in managing their liquidity.

Ruchi Gupta (2014) analyzed performance of Indian public sector banks using Camel approach for a five year period from 2009-13. They included all the 26 public sector banks in study. Inclusion of all 26 public sector banks in study, research tried to effetely measure the financial soundness of banks. Researcher employed the F-test and one way ANOVA for analysis and interpretation. The study revealed fact that there is a significant difference among overall performance of public sector banks. They also concluded that the banks with least ranking need to improve their performance to come up to the desired standards.

Mikail Altan, Habib Yusufazari & Aykut Beduk (2014) tried to attempt evaluate and analyzed performance of banks in Turkey using camel model. They have chosen three State-Owned banks and twelve Private-Owned banks from the Turkish banking sector, which represent more than seventy percent of the banking system in terms of total assets. They evaluated the financial performance of turkey banks through 23 ratios relating to CAMEL Model. They found that on the overall performance of, Ziraat Bank was on the top position followed by AK Bank and Vakit Bank. Study reveals fact that there is a significant difference between performance of state-owned and private-owned banks in Turkey

OBJECTIVE

Objectives of study are follows:

- Understand qualitative as well as quantitative factors for evaluating financial Banks
- To find the adequacy of CAMEL in capturing the overall performance of a Bank
- Analyze financial institutions and assign overall ratings through CAMEL model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this present study, an effort has been made to assess, evaluate and compare the financial performance of selected private sector banks. The present study of banks based on CAMEL methodology, which evaluates each and every component that is of important from the functioning of the Bank's perspective. The present study based on purely secondary data that

has been collected from annual reports of banks, magazines, articles published in journals, other published documents and websites have been chosen when found relevant. The study covers the period of 5 years i.e. year 2010-11 to year 2014-15. All the banks are ranked in the ascending/descending order based on individual bank sub-parameters.

The study includes comparison among following banks:

- ICICI Bank
- Axis Bank
- HDFC Bank
- Yes Bank
- Indusland Bank

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

CAMEL Model

1. Capital Adequacy

Capital adequacy is very prominent indicator to measure the financial strength of banking sector. High capital adequacies give enough confidence to stakeholders for their capital security. Capital adequacy shows the strength of bank to bear unexpected losses arise in near future.

i. Capital Adequacy Ratio(CAR)

Year	Capital Adequacy Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	19.54	12.65	16.22	16.50	15.89
2011-12	18.52	13.66	16.52	17.90	13.85
2012-13	18.74	17.00	16.80	18.30	15.36
2013-14	17.70	16.07	16.07	14.40	13.83
2014-15	17.02	15.09	16.79	15.60	12.09
Mean	18.30	14.89	16.48	16.54	14.20
Rank	1	4	3	2	5

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

It is found from the table that ICICI Bank (18.30) is No.1 in CAR followed by Yes (16.54) and HDFC Bank (16.48). Axis Bank also able to maintain mandatory CAR but stood on 4th rank. Indusland Bank gets lowest rank on CAR parameter.

ii. Debt – Equity Ratio

Year	Debt to Equity Ratio (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	6.08	11.34	8.79	13.87	9.87
2011-12	6.55	11.14	9.04	13.54	10.79
2012-13	6.57	8.96	9.09	15.13	8.34
2013-14	6.65	8.67	9.36	13.41	8.33
2014-15	6.64	9.00	8.00	10.05	8.91
Mean	6.50	9.82	8.85	13.20	9.25
Rank	1	4	2	5	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table show the Debt-Equity ratio of selected banks. ICICI Bank (6.50) gets 1st rank on Debt-Equity ratio which shows lower leverage of bank followed by HDFC Bank and Indusland Bank. Axis Bank and Yes Bank get 4th and 5th rank on Debt- Equity ratio which indicates these banks are maintaining high leverage.

iii. Advance to Assets Ratio

Year	Advances to Assets				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.53	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.57
2011-12	0.52	0.59	0.58	0.52	0.61
2012-13	0.54	0.58	0.61	0.47	0.60
2013-14	0.57	0.60	0.62	0.51	0.63
2014-15	0.60	0.61	0.62	0.55	0.63
Mean	0.55	0.59	0.60	0.53	0.61
Rank	4	3	2	5	1

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table indicates that Indusland Bank (1st) is very aggressive to lend its deposits to advance seekers which also mean that Indusland bank generating high profitability. HDFC (2nd) and Axis Bank (3rd) also performing good on advances to assets ratio compare to rivals ICICI (4th) and Yes banks (5th).

iv. Government Securities to Total Investment

Year	Government Securities to Total Investment (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	48.27	61.39	75.64	57.08	73.96
2011-12	54.77	62.81	78.19	58.29	81.68
2012-13	54.28	63.76	76.07	66.41	71.78
2013-14	54.17	61.30	78.25	54.77	71.33
2014-15	57.56	62.13	72.32	64.37	72.03
Mean	53.81	62.28	76.09	60.18	74.15
Rank	5	3	1	4	2

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table shows the government securities to total investment ratio. HDFC bank (1st) has invested its large part of total investment in the risk free government securities which indicate bank has strong risk free investment strategy. Indusland (2nd) and Axis Bank (3rd) also have good risk free investment strategies. Yes and ICICI bank get 4th and 5th rank respectively.

Composite Capital Adequacy

Bank	CAR	Debt-Equity Ratio	Advance to Assets Ratio	Government Securities to Total Investment	Group Rank	
	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank	Average	Rank
ICICI	1	1	4	5	2.75	2.5
Axis	4	4	3	3	3.5	4
HDFC	3	2	2	1	2	1
Yes	2	5	5	4	4	5
Indusland	5	3	1	2	2.75	2.5

On the basis of composite capital adequacy HDFC Bank get 1st position followed by ICICI and Indusland Bank combined 2.5 ranks. Axis and Yes bank got lowest rank 4th and 5th respectively. Reasons behind Yes lowest rank are the poor performance on Debt-Equity ratio and advance to assets ratio.

2. Assets Quality

Assets quality is an important financial indicator to measure the financial strength and health of banking sector. The objective behind the check assets quality is to know quality of assets

of bank, assets quality give indication that baking strength to employed assets in profitable project or not.

i. Net NPAs to Total Assets Ratio

Year	Net NPA's to Total Assets (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.59	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.16
2011-12	0.39	0.17	0.10	0.02	0.16
2012-13	0.42	0.21	0.12	0.01	0.19
2013-14	0.55	0.27	0.17	0.02	0.21
2014-15	0.97	0.29	0.15	0.06	0.19
Mean	0.58	0.19	0.13	0.03	0.18
Rank	5	4	2	1	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table show that Yes Bank gets 1st position followed by HDFC (2nd) rank and Indusland Bank (3rd) rank on Net NPAs to Total Assets. Performance of Axis (4th) and ICICI (5th) is poor on Net NPAs to Total Assets ratio.

ii. Net NPAs to Net Advances Ratio

Year	Net NPA's to Net Advances (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	1.11	0.29	0.19	0.03	0.28
2011-12	0.73	0.28	0.18	0.05	0.27
2012-13	0.77	0.36	0.20	0.01	0.31
2013-14	0.97	0.44	0.27	0.05	0.33
2014-15	1.61	0.46	0.25	0.12	0.31
Mean	1.04	0.37	0.22	0.05	0.30
Rank	5	4	2	1	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table show that Yes Bank gets 1st position followed by HDFC (2nd) rank and Indusland Bank (3rd) rank on Net NPAs to Net Advances. Performance of Axis (4th) and ICICI (5th) is poor on Net NPAs to Net Advances ratio. Table also indicates that Yes bank have powerful strategies to employed advances in secure hands.

iii. Total Investment to Total Assets Ratio (%)

Year	Total Investment to Total Assets Ratio (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	33.15	29.66	25.52	31.91	29.69
2011-12	32.63	32.63	28.58	37.68	25.30
2012-13	31.93	33.40	27.88	43.36	26.81
2013-14	29.77	29.63	24.60	37.56	24.78
2014-15	28.88	28.65	28.19	34.23	22.78
Mean	31.27	30.79	26.95	36.94	25.87
Rank	4	3	2	5	1

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Table indicates that financial performance of Indusland Bank followed by HDFC and Axis Bank is good on total investment to total assets ratio. These banks follow sage guard investment policy to protect its depositors. Indusland Bank get 1st rank followed HDFC and Axis Bank 2nd and 3rd ranks respectively. ICICI and Yes Bank get lowest rank 4th and 5th banks.

Composite Assets Quality

Bank	Net NPAs to Total Assets Ratio	Net NPA's to Net Advances Ratio	Total Investment to Total Assets Ratio	Group Rank	
	Rank	Rank	Rank	Average	Rank
ICICI	5	5	4	4.67	5
Axis	4	4	3	3.67	4
HDFC	2	2	2	2.00	1
Yes	1	1	5	2.33	2.5
Indusland	3	3	1	2.33	2.5

Above table show overall assets quality rank for banks. HDFC bank gets 1st rank on overall composite assets quality followed by Yes and Indusland Bank rank 2.5 equally. Axis and ICICI bank is the poor performer on composite assets quality. HDFC Bank performs well on net NPAs to total assets ratio and Net NPAs to Net Advances ratio. Yes bank performs better on above financial parameters. ICICI and Axis bank perform poor on above assets quality parameters.

3. Management Efficiency

Management efficiency is third component of the CAMEL model that measures the growth and management efficiency of bank to generate business and profitability. Management

efficiency shows that how much bank management or administrative is able to generate business and profits.

i. Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio

Year	Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.96	0.75	0.77	0.75	0.76
2011-12	0.99	0.77	0.79	0.77	0.83
2012-13	0.99	0.78	0.81	0.70	0.82
2013-14	0.95	0.82	0.82	0.75	0.91
2014-15	0.99	0.87	0.81	0.83	0.93
Mean	0.98	0.80	0.80	0.76	0.85
Rank	1	3.5	3.5	5	2

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show that ICICI bank gets top 1st rank on total advances to total deposits ratio which indicate that bank is flexible to providing advances out of its total deposits. ICICI bank is flexible to disburse 98% total deposits. Indusland bank also flexible to providing advances to loan seeker. Indusland bank gets 2nd rank on above total advances to total deposits ratio followed by Axis and HDFC bank. Yes bank is conservative in disburse of total deposits and poor performer on above parameters.

ii. Return on Net Worth Ratio

Year	Return on Net Worth				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	9.35	17.84	15.47	19.17	14.28
2011-12	10.70	18.60	17.27	20.89	16.97
2012-13	12.48	15.64	18.57	22.40	13.93
2013-14	13.40	16.27	19.50	22.72	15.59
2014-15	13.90	16.47	16.47	17.17	16.87
Mean	11.97	16.96	17.46	20.47	15.53
Rank	5	3	2	1	4

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the return on net worth ratio of banks from the year 2010-11 to 2014-15. Yes bank generate average 20.47% return on its equity which is highest among its rival banks and bank gets 1st rank on above parameter followed by HDFC and Axis Bank. Table shows

that HDFC and Axis bank also good performer on above parameter. Indusland Bank is good performer compare to its rival ICICI bank.

iii. Profit Per Employee

(Rs. Crore)

Year	Profit Per Employee				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	10.00	14.00	7.37	20.89	8.24
2011-12	11.00	14.00	8.00	20.42	8.57
2012-13	11.00	15.00	10.00	21.02	9.22
2013-14	14.00	15.00	12.00	20.45	9.03
2014-15	16.00	17.00	10.00	20.96	9.38
Mean	12.40	15.00	9.47	20.75	8.89
Rank	3	2	4	1	5

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table shows profit per employee of banks. Table indicates that Yes Employee is very well profit generator followed by Axis and ICICI bank. Yes, Axis and ICICI bank get 1st, 2nd, and 3rd position respectively on above parameter. HDFC and Indusland Bank employee are poor performing in generating profit per employee.

iv. Business Per Employee

(Rs. Crore)

Year	Business Per Employee				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	7.35	13.66	6.53	22.20	8.44
2011-12	7.08	12.76	6.54	17.48	7.88
2012-13	7.35	12.15	7.5	17.74	8.41
2013-14	7.47	12.30	8.9	15.58	7.17
2014-15	8.32	13.71	10.1	16.86	7.19
Mean	7.51	12.91	7.91	17.97	7.81
Rank	5	2	3	1	4

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the business per employee for banks. Yes bank employees are well performer on the above parameter. Yes bank gets 1st rank on above parameter followed by

Axis and HDFC bank. HDFC, Indusland and ICICI bank Performance on the above parameter averagely similar and poor.

Composite Management Efficiency

Bank	Total Advances to Total Deposits Ratio	Return on Net Worth	Profit Per Employee	Business Per Employee	Group Rank	
	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank	Average	Rank
ICICI	1	5	3	5	3.5	4
Axis	3.5	3	2	2	2.6	2
HDFC	3.5	2	4	3	3.1	3
Yes	5	1	1	1	2.0	1
Indusland	2	4	5	4	3.8	5

Above table shows composite earning quality. Yes bank is well performer on above parameter. Yes bank gets top position on above parameters followed by Axis and HDFC bank. Yes bank performs better on return on net worth, profit per employee and business per employee. Axis bank gets 2nd rank on above composite management efficiency and HDFC bank gets 3rd rank. ICICI (4th) and Indusland bank (5th) perform poor on management efficiency component.

4. Earning Efficiency

The earning efficiency is another component of CAMEL model. Earning quality represents the quality of bank's profitability and bank capability to maintain quality and earn consistently. Earning efficiency show the earning trends of banks its future prospects.

i. Percentage Growth in Net Profit

Year	Percentage Growth in net profit				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	27.99	34.76	33.16	52.21	64.80
2011-12	25.51	25.19	31.60	34.40	39.02
2012-13	28.77	22.09	30.25	33.13	32.22
2013-14	17.84	20.05	26.00	24.40	32.68
2014-15	13.91	18.34	20.50	23.96	27.39
Mean	22.80	24.09	28.30	33.62	39.22
Rank	5	4	3	2	1

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the trend in net profit. All banks show increasing trend in net profit. Indusland bank gets the 1st rank among its rival on percentage growth in net profit. Indusland bank shows average 39.22% growth in net profit. Yes and HDFC bank get 2nd and 3rd rank respectively. Axis and ICICI bank show good performance on above parameter individually but poor performer comparatively its rivals.

ii. Net Interest Margin

Year	Net Interest Margin (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	2.64	3.65	4.30	2.90	3.47
2011-12	2.73	3.59	4.20	2.80	3.33
2012-13	3.11	3.53	4.50	2.90	3.43
2013-14	3.33	3.81	4.40	2.90	3.71
2014-15	3.48	3.92	4.40	3.20	3.65
Mean	3.06	3.70	4.36	2.94	3.52
Rank	4	2	1	5	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the net interest margin for banks. HDFC bank gets 1st on above net interest margin followed by its Axis, Indusland and ICICI bank 2nd, 3rd, 4th rank respectively. Yes bank performs poor on above parameter and gets lower rank.

iii. Net Profit to Total Assets Ratio

Year	Net Profit to Total Assets (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.97	1.40	1.42	1.23	1.27
2011-12	1.04	1.49	1.53	1.33	1.39
2012-13	1.23	1.52	1.68	1.31	1.45
2013-14	1.31	1.61	1.72	1.48	1.62
2014-15	1.35	1.57	1.73	1.47	1.64
Mean	1.18	1.52	1.62	1.37	1.47
Rank	5	2	1	4	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the net profit to total assets for banks. It is inferred from the table HDFC bank is performing well on above net profit to total assets. HDFC bank gets top position

followed by Axis and Indusland bank 2nd and 3rd rank respectively. Yes and ICICI bank gets 4th and 5th rank respectively on net profit to total assets ratio.

iv. Operating Profit to Total Assets

Year	Operating Profit to Total Assets (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	2.23	2.64	2.94	2.02	2.50
2011-12	2.12	2.60	2.78	2.09	2.51
2012-13	2.46	2.73	2.85	2.16	2.61
2013-14	2.79	2.99	2.92	2.47	3.10
2014-15	3.05	2.90	2.87	2.39	2.96
Mean	2.53	2.77	2.87	2.22	2.74
Rank	4	2	1	5	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table shows the operating profit to total assets ratio for selected banks. HDFC bank gets top position on above selected earning efficiency parameter. Axis and Indusland bank respectively gets 2nd and 3rd rank above parameter respectively. ICICI and Yes bank is also performing good on above parameter but get 4th and 5th rank respectively.

v. Interest Income to Total Income

Year	Interest Income to Total Income (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	79.62	76.59	82.13	86.64	83.41
2011-12	81.72	80.23	83.88	88.04	84.12
2012-13	82.76	80.58	83.65	86.84	83.67
2013-14	80.90	80.54	83.86	85.29	81.36
2014-15	80.13	80.92	84.34	84.97	80.13
Mean	81.03	79.77	83.57	86.35	82.54
Rank	4	5	2	1	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table shows interest income to total income for banks. Yes bank gets 1st position on above parameters. It is inferred from the table that 86% interest income contributes in total income for the Yes bank. HDFC and Indusland bank gets 2nd and 3rd position respectively on above parameter and 83% and 82% interest income contribute in total income for HDFC and Indusland Bank respectively. ICICI and Axis bank get 4th and 5th rank respectively.

Composite Earning Efficiency

Bank	Percentage Growth in net profit	Net Interest Margin	Net Profit to Total Assets	Operating Profit to Total Assets	Interest Income to Total Income	Group Rank	
	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank	Average	Rank
ICICI	5	4	5	4	4	4.4	5
Axis	4	2	2	2	5	3.0	3
HDFC	3	1	1	1	2	1.6	1
Yes	2	5	4	5	1	3.4	4
Indusland	1	3	3	3	3	2.6	2

Above table shows composite earning efficiency for banks. HDFC bank gets top position on above composite earning efficiency and contributory factors are net interest margin, net profit to total assets, operating profits to total assets and interest income to total income. Indusland and Axis bank get 2nd and 3rd position respectively. Yes and ICICI bank gets 4th and 5th rank respectively.

5. Liquidity

Risk of liquidity can have an effect on the image of bank. Liquidity is a crucial aspect which reflects bank's ability to meet its financial obligations. An adequate liquidity position means a situation, where organization can obtain sufficient liquid funds, either by increasing liabilities or by converting its assets quickly into cash (Misra & Aspal, 2013).

i. Loans to Deposit Ratio

Year	Loan to Deposit Ratio				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	0.49	0.14	0.07	0.15	0.16
2011-12	0.55	0.15	0.10	0.29	0.20
2012-13	0.50	0.17	0.11	0.31	0.17
2013-14	0.47	0.18	0.11	0.29	0.24
2014-15	0.48	0.25	0.10	0.29	0.28
Mean	0.49	0.18	0.10	0.26	0.21
Rank	5	2	1	4	3

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table shows loan to deposit ratio for banks. HDFC bank gets 1st position on above parameter followed by Axis and Indusland Bank. Yes and ICICI bank gets 4th and 5th position on above parameter.

ii. Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio

Year	Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	8.39	8.82	10.73	5.92	8.82
2011-12	7.65	4.88	6.21	4.87	9.62
2012-13	7.72	6.00	6.81	4.10	9.34
2013-14	6.98	7.37	8.05	5.40	7.78
2014-15	6.55	7.81	6.15	5.55	9.88
Mean	7.46	6.98	7.59	5.17	9.09
Rank	3	4	2	5	1

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table shows the liquid assets to total assets ratio for selected banks. It is inferred from the table that 9% liquid assets to total assets for Indusland bank and Indusland bank get 1st rank on above parameter followed by HDFC and ICICI bank. Axis and Yes bank get 4th and 5th rank respectively.

iii. Liquid Assets to Total Deposit Ratio

Year	Liquid Assets to Total Deposit Ratio (%)				
	Banks				
	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank	HDFC Bank	Yes Bank	Indusland Bank
2010-11	15.11	11.31	14.30	7.61	11.71
2011-12	14.18	6.33	8.58	7.29	13.08
2012-13	14.15	8.09	9.21	6.07	12.66
2013-14	12.51	10.05	10.78	7.94	11.19
2014-15	11.70	11.20	8.06	8.29	14.54
Mean	13.53	9.40	10.19	7.44	12.63
Rank	1	4	3	5	2

Source: Compiled from annual report of selected private banks.

Above table show the liquid assets to total deposit ratio for banks. ICICI, Indusland and HDFC bank get 1st, 2nd, and 3rd position respectively. Axis and Yes bank get 4th and 5th rank respectively on liquid assets to total deposit ratio.

Composite Liquidity

Bank	Loan to Deposit Ratio	Liquid Assets to Total Assets Ratio	Liquid Assets to Total Deposit Ratio	Group Rank	
	Rank	Rank	Rank	Average	Rank
ICICI	5	3	1	3.0	3
Axis	2	4	4	3.3	4
HDFC	1	2	3	2.0	1.5
Yes	4	5	5	4.7	5
Indusland	3	1	2	2.0	1.5

Above table show the composite liquidity for banks. HDFC and Indusland Bank tie first position and get 1.5 ranks respectively. ICICI, Axis and Yes bank get 3rd, 4th, and 5th rank respectively.

Composite Ranking (overall performance) of Banks

Bank	C	A	M	E	L	Average	Rank
ICICI Bank	2.75	4.67	3.50	4.40	3.00	3.66	5
Axis Bank	3.50	3.67	2.60	3.00	3.30	3.21	3
HDFC Bank	2.00	2.00	3.10	1.60	2.00	2.14	1
Yes Bank	4.00	2.33	2.00	3.40	4.70	3.29	4
Indusland Bank	2.75	2.33	3.80	2.60	2.00	2.70	2

Above composite ranking table show the overall performance of banks on Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management Efficiency, Earning Efficiency and Liquidity CAMEL parameters. It is inferred from the table that HDFC overall performance is excellent and bank got 1st position out of five banks. Indusland bank overall rank is 2nd followed by Axis and Yes bank. Axis and Yes Bank got 3rd and 4th rank respectively. ICICI bank performs poorly on overall ranking and got 5th position.

FINDINGS

In is found from the Capital Adequacy component that HDFC Bank is performance is better than its rival bank. ICICI and Indusland bank also performing well on Capital adequacy component.

Further, it is found from another Assets quality component that HDFC bank performing well on Assets quality. Yes and Indusland bank also performing well on Assets quality component.

Study also reveals that Yes bank performing well on management efficiency followed by Axis and HDFC bank.

It is also found from earning efficiency component that HDFC bank performing well followed by its rival Indusland and Axis bank.

Overall liquidity of HDFC bank and Indusland bank is good. Overall liquidity of ICICI bank is also better.

CONCLUSION

CAMEL model provides overall performance picture of bank on different parameters from Capital adequacy to liquidity. It is found from the study that to measure and analyze the performance of bank is very interesting and challenging. Study reveals that overall performance of HDFC Bank is excellent and HDFC Bank got 1st among its rival banks. It is also concluded that Indusland and Axis Bank performance on CAMEL component is good.

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